

Exploring the Relationship between Authentic Leadership, Organisational Citizenship Behaviour and Job Crafting of Nurses: A Case Study from Vhembe District, Limpopo Province, South Africa

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This study explored the relationship between authentic leadership, organisational citizenship behaviour, and job crafting among nurses in the Vhembe District, Limpopo Province, South Africa. Data were collected from 50 nurses through a quantitative research approach using structured questionnaires. The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between authentic leadership and OCB and between authentic leadership and job crafting. These results suggest that nurses who perceive their leaders as authentic are more likely to engage in organisational citizenship behaviours and craft their job roles to align with their strengths and preferences. This study highlights the importance of fostering authentic leadership in healthcare settings to enhance nurses' well-being and organisational effectiveness.

Keywords: Authentic leadership, organisational citizenship behaviour, job crafting, healthcare leadership

The healthcare sector, particularly nursing, is one of the most demanding fields in terms of emotional and physical labour. Africa, especially South Africa, provides a unique context for the fraternity of public health care services. Wrzesniewski et al. (2010) contend that most nurses employed by public hospitals face difficulties, including scarce resources and heavy workloads, which impact their productivity, well-being and general function. With nurses playing a critical role in patient care, understanding the factors that influence their performance, engagement, and well-being is essential. Recent studies have focused on leadership styles and their impact on employee behaviours such as organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) and job crafting. Peredes et al. (2021) state that job crafting, Organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB), and authentic leadership are three significant concepts that organisational studies focus on. Therefore, these constructs are essential in nursing because they enhance nurses' and their organisations' general effectiveness and well-being (Atwijuka & Caldwell, 2017).

The healthcare system in South Africa presents a unique case. It is a dual system with private and public healthcare systems running in parallel. The prevailing conditions denote a well-resourced private Healthcare system, catering for a fraction of the population and an

under-resourced public healthcare system catering for most of the population. According to Statistics South Africa (STATS SA) (2023), 84% (approximately 53 million) of the South African Population rely on the public healthcare system, while 16% (approximately 9.8 million) of the South African population rely on the private healthcare system. This has consequently overburdened the public healthcare givers with excessive workload, with few resources at their disposal. Be that as it may, the Republic of South Africa's parliament has legislated the National Health Insurance Act 20 of 2023 (NHI), assented to by President Cyril Ramaphosa on May 15, 2024, which establishes the legal foundation for South Africa's transition toward Universal Health Coverage (UHC). The NHI was introduced against the backdrop of Universal Health Coverage having emerged as a critical policy imperative within the global health governance framework, following the World Health Organisation's endorsement of UHC as a fundamental component of the Sustainable Development Goals. Notwithstanding, it is yet to be implemented, thus the South African healthcare system remains unevenly fractured into private and public healthcare. This study focuses on the public healthcare system, being the system that is adversely impacted by the status quo. It explores the relationship between authentic leadership, organisational citizenship behaviour and job crafting of nurses in Vhembe District, Limpopo province, South Africa.

Authentic leadership, which emphasises transparency, ethical behaviour, and genuine relationships between leaders and subordinates, has been identified as a key factor in fostering a positive work environment. Meanwhile, Bolino et al. (2015) define organisational citizenship behaviour as discretionary actions that go beyond formal job requirements and contribute to the organisation's overall functioning. In nursing, this could involve assisting colleagues, taking on additional responsibilities, or improving patient care. On the other hand, job crafting is defined by Peredes et al. (2021) as the process through which employees modify their job roles to suit their skills, preferences, and needs. Both OCB and job

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crafting are essential for enhancing job satisfaction and organisational effectiveness in the healthcare sector. Kazemipour and Amin (2012) reported that nurses occasionally showed unwillingness to participate in organisational citizenship activities. Therefore, examining job crafting, organisational citizenship behaviour and authentic leadership in public hospitals provide valuable knowledge for fostering a positive work atmosphere, boosting nurses' well-being, and resolving organisational issues.

Thus, this study aims to explore the relationship between authentic leadership, OCB, and job crafting among nurses in the Vhembe District, Limpopo Province, South Africa. Specifically, the study seeks to determine whether authentic leadership influences nurses' willingness to engage in OCB and job crafting behaviours, thereby contributing to a positive work environment.

Review of Literature

Authentic Leadership

Authentic leadership is a style of leadership that emphasises self-awareness, transparency, ethical conduct, and the development of genuine relationships between leaders and subordinates. It has been shown to foster trust, encourage open communication, and improve employee engagement (Atwijuka & Caldwell, 2017). In nursing, where employees often face high-stress situations, authentic leadership can help create a supportive environment that enhances job satisfaction and performance (Wong & Cummings, 2009). According to Davidson et al. (2017), authentic leadership is crucial for boosting nurses' morale and enhancing patient outcomes. It helps them reestablish confidence, develop self-assurance, foster clear associations, and promote trust and accountability. Similarly, Atwijuka and Caldwell (2017) contend that authentic leadership in nursing is associated with higher levels of patient care commitment, decreased rates of burnout, and better job satisfaction for nurses.

In parentheses, Davidson et al. (2017) further articulate that other contextual factors, including organisational culture and organisational structure, can mediate how authentic leadership affects subordinates. Additionally, intrinsic factors such as emotional intelligence and a lifelong process of personal development become essential in shaping the emergence of authentic leadership (Davidson et al., 2017). Furthermore, the resources and organisational support that leaders receive can impact their capacity to lead honestly (Atwijuka & Caldwell, 2017). Therefore, to foster authentic leadership, one must prioritise relationships, take contextual factors into account, embrace personal values and ethics, develop emotional intelligence, cultivate self-awareness, promote transparency and openness, and engage in personal development (Datta, 2015). This study thus conceptualises Authentic leadership from Walumbwa et al. (2008) definition that identifies self-awareness, strong moral code, relational transparency, and balanced processing as four main dimensions of authentic leadership.

Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB)

Organisational citizenship behaviour is conceptualised from the notion of willingness to cooperate (Barnard, 1938) and innovative and spontaneous behaviours (Katz & Kahn, 1978) and finally through a formative definition posited by Organ (1988, p. 4) as a "discretionary individual behaviour, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system and which as a whole

promotes the effective functioning of the organization". Organ (1997, P.59) later redefined OCB as "activities that support the social and psychological environment in which the performance of tasks has a place". Noting that OCB has been conceptualised as discretionary and not enforceable, Pickford and Joy (2016) view it as an expression of individual motivation within a group or organisational context.

Therefore, Organisational Citizenship Behaviour is a voluntary behaviour that is not formally required by an organisation but contributes to its overall success. In nursing, OCB might involve helping colleagues, taking on extra tasks, or showing initiative that improves patient care (Bolino et al., 2015). Research has demonstrated that employees who perceive their leaders as trustworthy and supportive are more likely to engage in OCB (Alkahtani, 2015). As Kazemipour and Amin (2012) allude, organisational citizenship behaviour reduces the amount of time managers spend on basic tasks and lessens the need for regulation, thus freeing up more time for strategic tasks. Bacaksiz et al. (2017) further note that employees' OCB and job-crafting behaviours are greatly influenced by authentic leadership. This notion is supported by Atwijuka and Caldwell (2017) in their assertion that a culture of trust, openness, and support created by authentic leaders encourages employees to go above and beyond their call of duty. Therefore, the likelihood of nurses participating in organisational citizenship activities, such as helping coworkers, exchanging expertise, and encouraging team members, is higher when they perceive their leaders as trustworthy. Organ (1998) identifies five main dimensions of organisational citizenship behaviour as follows: altruism (helping colleagues), generalised compliance (conscientiousness or commitment), courtesy (engaging in proactive problem-solving), civic virtue (showing loyalty through constructive involvement in governance issues), and sportsmanship (willingness to forgo minor inconveniences without complains). The dynamic nature of OCB definitions makes it difficult to delineate its dimensions. Various traits have been attributed to the causes or predictors of OCB (Somech & Drach-Zahavy, 2004) where Podaskoff et al. (2000) for example, condensed the more than 30 types of citizenship behaviour found in the literature into 7: helping behaviours, sportsmanship, organisational loyalty, organisational compliance, individual initiative, civic virtue, and self-development. This research focused on four main dimensions (Helping colleagues, commitment, demonstrating loyalty & engaging in proactive problem-solving) that are contextually helpful to analyse OCB.

Job Crafting

The foundational conceptualisation of job crafting emanates from two main perspectives, being the original job crafting theory by Wrzesniewski and Dutton (2001) and the job demand resources perspective by Tims et al. (2012). Wrzesniewski and Dutton (2001, p.179) define job crafting as "the physical and cognitive changes individuals make in the task or relational boundaries of their work. This perspective lays the foundation for the identification of the three core dimensions of Job crafting, namely, Task 1 (changing the number, scope or types of tasks done at work), relational crafting (changing the quality/amount of interaction with others at work), and cognitive crafting (altering how one frames or views the job). Tims et al. (2012) provide a second perspective on job crafting, derived from the job demand-resource theory (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). Tims et al (2012, p.174) define job crafting as "the changes

that employees may make to balance their job demands and job resources with their abilities and needs". Although the two perspectives provide a theoretical foundation for job crafting, Zhang and Parker (2018) contents that they differ in how they define the content of crafting, with Wrzesniewski and Dutton (2001) focusing on changes in task/relational/cognitive boundaries, whereas Tims et al. (2012) focused on changes in job characteristics. While this research is grounded in the seminal conceptualisation of job crafting established by Wrzesniewski and Dutton (2001) it acknowledges the theoretical evolution and conceptual refinement that have characterised this construct over the past two decades. Contemporary scholarship has witnessed the emergence of several sophisticated frameworks that have expanded the traditional three-dimensional nomenclature, including promotion and prevention job crafting paradigms (Lichtenthaler & Fischbach, 2018), role-based and resource-based avoidance job crafting (Bruning & Campion, 2018), and approach-avoidance job crafting dichotomies (Zhang & Parker, 2019).

Consequently, this study integrates intellectual crafting as a fourth dimension, which, despite its absence from the original three-dimensional framework proposed by Wrzesniewski and Dutton (2001) has gained empirical support in recent literature as a distinct theoretical extension. Intellectual crafting encompasses employees' proactive engagement with knowledge acquisition, learning processes, and problem-solving activities inherent in their work roles.

Job crafting allows employees to reshape their job roles by altering their tasks, relationships, or perceptions of their work. This proactive approach enables individuals to tailor their roles to align with their strengths and values, resulting in increased job satisfaction and well-being (Wrzesniewski & Dutton, 2001). In healthcare, job crafting can help nurses cope with the demands of their work by giving them a sense of control over their roles (Tims & Bakker, 2010). This conception of job crafting is situated within the broader framework of the job demands capital model, according to Bakker and Demerouti (2017). Romeo et al. (2021) posit that job crafting enables nurses to experience autonomy, meaningfulness, and control over their work, thereby increasing engagement.

Notwithstanding their mandate to provide patients with daily care, healthcare personnel experience high levels of challenges. By proactively applying organisational principles that support job crafting and enable a dynamic and laid-back operational environment, these challenges can be somewhat tackled (Bacaksiz, Tuna, & Seren, 2017). Moreover, by modifying the physical, mental, and social aspects of the working action, job crafting enables nurses to create job models (Romeo et al., 2021). Thus, a growing body of research has looked at a variety of behaviours to encourage employees to craft their jobs.

The Relationship Between Authentic Leadership, OCB, and Job Crafting

Studies have shown that authentic leadership positively influences both OCB and job crafting. Leaders who demonstrate ethical behaviour, transparency, and a genuine concern for their employees' well-being foster a work environment where employees feel empowered to go beyond their formal duties and craft their roles to better suit their needs (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). This study builds on this existing literature by exploring these relationships in the context of public hospitals in South Africa, the Vhembe district of Limpopo province in particular. According to Sri Ramalu and

Janadari (2022), there is a positive relationship between OCB and authentic leadership. Furthermore, Basirudin et al. (2016) contend that authentic leaders among nurses foster an atmosphere that motivates and inspires nurses to engage in adaptable behaviours that benefit the institution. Authentic leaders help to create an environment where OCB flourish by setting an example, establishing trust, supporting meaningful work, cultivating pleasant psychological states, and promoting reciprocity (Wong & Cummings, 2009). There is a reciprocal relationship between job crafting, OCB, and authentic leadership. Genuine leaders who foster an environment of conviction and psychological safety are likely to experience a demonstration of organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) and job crafting from their subordinates.

According to Wong and Cummings (2009), nurses who have a strong feeling of commitment to their healthcare institutions are more likely to exhibit organisational citizenship behaviours. Similarly, Workers' desire to engage in OCB is generally influenced by their opinions on workplace justice, including distributive, procedural, and interactional justice (Ahmad & Zafar, 2018). Therefore, they are more willing to engage in actions that help the organisation when they have faith in their leaders because they know their contributions will be appreciated and acknowledged.

Theoretical Framework

This research adopts a multi-theoretical approach, integrating three theoretical paradigms to understand the interrelationships among authentic leadership, organisational citizenship behaviour, and job crafting. The study is grounded in Authentic Leadership Theory (Avolio & Gardner, 2005; Walumbwa et al., 2008) which suggests that authentic leaders demonstrate genuine self-awareness, relational transparency, balanced processing, and moral perspective, thereby fostering trust and positive organisational outcomes through their consistent alignment of values, beliefs, and behaviours. The conceptualisation of organisational citizenship behaviour is based on Organisational Justice Theory (Greenberg, 1987; Colquitt et al., 2001) which elucidates how employees' perceptions of fairness across distributive, procedural, and interactional dimensions influence their discretionary prosocial behaviours that extend beyond formal role requirements and thereby contribute to organisational effectiveness. Finally, the job crafting construct is theoretically located within the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007; Demerouti et al., 2001) which provides a comprehensive framework for understanding how employees proactively modify their job demands and resources to optimise their work environment, enhance well-being, and achieve sustainable performance. This theoretical triangulation enables a nuanced examination of how authentic leadership behaviours may influence employees' perceptions of organisational justice, subsequently motivating citizenship behaviours, while simultaneously empowering employees to engage in various forms of job crafting to align their work experiences with their values and capabilities. The integration of these complementary theoretical perspectives provides a robust foundation for understanding the complex dynamics between leadership authenticity, employee justice perceptions, discretionary organisational behaviours, and proactive work redesign activities. Based on the discussed empirical review and stated hypotheses, the following conceptual framework on the link between authentic leadership, organisational citizenship behaviour and job crafting was developed. See Figure 1 below.

Figure 1*The Conceptual Framework**Objectives of the Study*

- To explore the relationship between authentic leadership, OCB, and job crafting among nurses in the Vhembe District, Limpopo Province, South Africa.
- To determine whether authentic leadership influences nurses' willingness to engage in OCB and job-crafting behaviours

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H1*: There is a significant statistical relationship between authentic leadership, organisational citizenship and job crafting of nurses in the Vhembe District, Limpopo Province, South Africa.
- *H2*: Authentic leadership influences organisational citizenship behaviour and job crafting behaviour of nurses in the Vhembe District, Limpopo Province, South Africa.

Method*Participants and Data Collection*

The target population for this study consisted of full-time nurses at healthcare institutions in Vhembe District, Limpopo Province, South Africa. A total of 50 nurses were selected using stratified random sampling to participate in the study. The participants were classified into full-time and part-time strata. A sample of 50 participants was drawn from a population of 286 using Slovin's formula, $n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$ (Ryan, 2013), to calculate the sample size. (n = Sample size, N = Population size, e = Margin of error, where $n = 286 / (1 + 286 \times 0.132) = 49.028$). Data were collected using structured questionnaires, which were used to measure authentic leadership, OCB, and job crafting. The questionnaires were distributed electronically via Google Forms to accommodate the nurses' schedules and workload. The standard ethical clearance procedure was strictly followed before the distribution of the questionnaires, where permission to conduct this study was granted by the following sectors and stakeholders: the University of Venda Research Ethics Committee, the Limpopo Provincial Department of Health, as well as the Vhembe district public hospitals.

Research Design

A quantitative research approach was adopted for this study, utilising a cross-sectional survey design. The research was conducted at

healthcare institutions located in the Vhembe District of the Limpopo Province, South Africa. The primary objective was to investigate the relationship between authentic leadership, OCB, and job crafting among nurses. Apuke (2017) also employed a quantitative study methodology to evaluate and explore the relationship between job crafting, organisational citizenship behaviour, and authentic leadership. The motivation for this design is that the use of a questionnaire allows for the collection of information from participants, provides a consistent recording of responses, and helps in processing the received data (Apuke, 2017).

Measures

Authentic Leadership Questionnaire (Avolio et al., 2010): This 16-item questionnaire assessed nurses' perceptions of their leaders' authenticity. The Authentic Leadership Questionnaires were rated on a 6-point Likert scale, ranging from (1) *strongly disagreeing* to (5) *definitely agree*.

Organisational Citizenship Behaviour Questionnaire (Spector et al., 2010): This 10-item scale measured nurses' engagement in OCB. The organisational citizenship behaviour questionnaire assesses the prevalence of good citizenship practices in the workplace, where replies were scored using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (*never*) to 5 (*every day*).

Job Crafting Questionnaire (Slemp & Vella-Brodrick, 2013): This 15-item scale assessed the extent to which nurses engage in job crafting behaviours, and it was rated on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from (1) *strongly disagreeing* to (5) *firmly agreeing*.

Table 1*Reliability Statistics*

Authentic Leadership Questionnaires	
Cronbach's Alpha	Number of items
0.868	16
Organisational Citizenship Behaviour Questionnaires	
Cronbach's Alpha	Number of items
0.835	14
Job Crafting Questionnaires	
Cronbach's Alpha	Number of items
0.893	20

The reliability tests for all three questionnaires were run using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 29) to measure the internal inter-item consistency. All three scales reported Cronbach alpha coefficients that comply with the cut-off of $\alpha \geq 0.70$ (Pallant, 2016). The Cronbach alpha coefficients are displayed in the above table.

Data Analysis

The data were analysed using SPSS version 29. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, mean, Standard deviations, Cronbach alpha coefficients, skewness, kurtosis) were calculated to summarise the demographic data and determine their normality. Pearson product-moment correlation coefficients were used to test the relationships between authentic leadership, OCB, and job crafting. These statistical methods were used to realise the research objectives and to test the research hypothesis.

Ethical Considerations (Informed Consent, Permission, Confidentiality & Anonymity)

Irena (2018) states that when people participate in a study or when

complex information is assembled, moral considerations assessed by a research ethics committee are unquestionably relevant. The Ethics Committee upholds the values, well-being, and welfare of research participants and promotes morally sound, inclusive research. This study observed the University's standard ethical procedure, starting with securing permission to conduct the research, ensuring that the respondents had voluntarily consented to participating in the study and preventing any form of harm to the respondents. The permissions were sought and granted by the University's Research Ethics Committee, the Limpopo provincial department of health, and the Vhembe district public hospitals. The respondents were informed of the details and intentions of the research and thus consented to voluntary participation in the study. Moreover, the information attained by the researcher from respondents remained confidential, and the identities of the respondents were never divulged.

Results

Table 2

Gender

	Frequency	Percent
Male	14	28.0
Female	36	72.0
Total	50	100.0

Table 2 summarises the gender statistics of the participants, with 14 (28%) being males and 36 (72%) being females.

Table 3

Age Group

	Frequency	Percent
20-39 Years	11	22.0
40-59 years	37	74.0
60 years and above	2	4.0
Total	50	100.0

Table 3 indicates that, out of the 50 respondents, 11 (22%) were within the age range of 20 - 39 years; 37 (74%) fell within the 40 - 59 age range, while 2 (4%) were within the age range of years and above age range.

Table 4

Characteristics of Respondents by Age Group and Gender

Years	Male	Female	Total
20-39 years	5	6	11
40-59 years	8	29	37
60+ years	1	1	2
Total	14	36	50

Table 4 presents a cross-tabulation analysis examining the demographic composition of the study sample across gender and age cohorts, thereby facilitating an examination of the distributional patterns within these variables. The cross-tabulation matrix illustrates the frequency distribution of participants across each intersection of gender and age categories within the research sample.

The demographic analysis reveals distinct patterns in the gender-age distribution among the participants. Male respondents ($n = 14$)

demonstrated the following age distribution: 35.7% ($n = 5$) were classified within the 20-39 years cohort, 57.1% ($n = 8$) belonged to the 40-59 years demographic, and 7.1% ($n = 1$) were categorized within the 60 years and above age group. Conversely, female participants ($n = 36$) exhibited a different distributional pattern: 16.7% ($n = 6$) fell within the 20-39 years age bracket, 80.6% ($n = 29$) were positioned in the 40-59 years category, and 2.8% ($n = 1$) belonged to the 60 years and above demographic segment.

Figure 1

Qualifications of Respondents

Figure 1 displays the qualifications of the respondents. Of the 50 respondents, two (2) had matric as their highest qualification; seventeen (17) had a national diploma; twenty-two (22) had Advance diplomas or Bachelors' degree; seven (7) had a Postgraduate diploma or Honours degree; two (2) held a Masters' degree, while no respondent had a doctoral (PhD) degree.

Figure 2

Working Experience

Regarding the working experience (as displayed in figure 2), four respondents (4) had a service range of between 0 to 2 years; three respondents (3) had worked for a period of 2 to 5 years; four respondents had worked for a period of 5 to 10 years, whereas fifteen respondents had worked for a period of 10 to 15 years.

Table 5 presents the descriptive statistics for the 12 sub-dimensions derived from the three primary constructs examined in this study. The dimensional structure comprises four sub-dimensions operationalised through the Authentic Leadership Questionnaire (ALQ), four sub-dimensions measured via the Organisational Citizenship Behaviour Questionnaire (OCBQ), and four sub-dimensions assessed using the Job Crafting Questionnaire (JCQ).

Table 5
Descriptive Statistics of the 14 Sub-dimensions

	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient	Mean	Std Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
1. Rational Transparency	.681- .60	22.06	6.07	0.33	-0.20
2. Balanced Processing	.789- .70	1.70	0.65	0.38	-0.65
3. Strong Moral Code	.892- .70	2.50	1.25	0.52	-1.00
4. Self-awareness	.793- .70	1.60	0.83	2.00	5.40
5. Engaging in proactive problem-solving	.757- .70	13.70	4.30	1.30	4.00
6. Helping Colleague	.752- .70	6.26	2.00	0.20	-1.40
7. Commitment	.868- .70	7.02	2.00	-0.03	-0.80
8. Demonstrating Loyalty	.780- .70	3.98	1.40	0.70	1.30
9. Task Crafting	.735- .60	32.08	8.50	0.02	-0.70
10. Cognitive Crafting	.765- .70	3.64	1.54	1.60	4.90
11. Relational Crafting	.881- .70	1.70	0.68	0.86	1.40
12. Intellectual Crafting	.787- .70	1.62	0.70	0.62	-0.60

The descriptive analysis demonstrates that the dataset exhibited characteristics consistent with normal distribution, with values clustering within the range of -0.3 to 6.21, indicating a right-skewed distribution that met the parametric assumptions necessary for subsequent statistical analyses. Table 5 further delineates the

descriptive statistics and internal consistency reliability coefficients (Cronbach's alpha) for each dimensional component across the three primary constructs: authentic leadership, organizational citizenship behaviour, and job crafting.

Table 6
Correlation Coefficient

Item	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1. Rational Transparency	-	0.00*	0.64	0.00*	0.42	0.00*	0.01*	0.01*	0.00*	0.00*	0.13
2. Balanced Processing	0.00*	-	0.06	0.49	0.37	0.02*	0.25	0.22	0.26	0.42	0.81
3. Strong moral code	0.64	0.06	-	0.12	0.75	0.50	0.88	0.77	0.73	0.45	0.55
4. EPS	0.01*	0.49	0.12	-	0.12	0.00*	0.12	0.03*	0.04*	0.42	0.81
5. Vulnerability	0.11	0.12	0.75	0.12	-	0.80	0.31	0.89	0.56	0.51	0.72
6. Helping colleagues	0.00*	0.02*	0.50	0.00*	0.80	-	0.16	0.34	0.00*	0.01*	0.06
7. Commitment	0.01*	0.25	0.88	0.10	0.31	0.16	-	0.18	0.00*	0.02*	0.03*
8. Demonstrating loyalty	0.01*	0.22	0.07	0.03*	0.89	0.13	0.19	-	0.12	0.96	0.41
9. Task crafting	0.00*	0.36	0.73	0.04*	0.56	0.03*	0.00*	0.12	-	0.00*	0.00*
10. Rational crafting	0.00*	0.42	0.45	0.42	0.09	0.01*	0.02*	0.96	0.00*	-	0.00*
11. Intellectual crafting	0.13	0.81	0.55	0.81	0.72	0.06	0.03*	0.41	0.00*	0.00	-

Note. *Statistically significant: $p \leq 0.05$ (EPS = Engaging in proactive problem solving)

The Pearson correlation analysis presented in Table 6 demonstrates statistically significant positive associations between authentic leadership dimensions and both organisational citizenship behaviour and job crafting among nursing personnel. The findings reveal that nurses' perceptions of authentic leadership in their supervisors were positively associated with increased engagement in organisational citizenship behaviours and job crafting activities.

Specifically, Relational Transparency exhibited robust positive correlations with multiple dependant variables, including Helping Colleagues ($r = .614, p < .001$), Commitment ($r = .342, p < .001$), Engaging in Proactive Problem Solving ($r = .458, p < .001$), Demonstrating Loyalty ($r = .334, p < .01$), Task Crafting ($r = .596, p < .001$), and Relational Crafting ($r = .456, p < .001$).

Balanced Processing demonstrated significant positive associations with Helping Colleagues ($r = .321, p < .05$).

Additionally, Engaging in Proactive Problem Solving showed positive correlations with Helping Colleagues ($r = .480, p < .001$), Demonstrating Loyalty ($r = .299, p < .05$), and Task Crafting ($r = .284, p < .05$). Commitment was positively correlated with Relational Crafting ($r = .511, p < .001$), Task Crafting ($r = .327, p < .05$), and Cognitive Crafting ($r = .301, p < .05$). Furthermore, Helping Colleagues exhibited positive associations with Relational Crafting ($r = .409, p < .001$) and Task Crafting ($r = .337, p < .01$).

The significance levels are denoted by * for $p \leq 0.05$. Interpretation involves considering both the strength and direction of correlations. Following Cohen's (1988) effect size conventions for correlation coefficients, where small effects are denoted by $r \geq 0.10$, medium effects by $r \geq 0.30$, and large effects by $r \geq 0.50$, the observed correlations predominantly demonstrate medium to large effect sizes. These findings provide empirical support for

statistically significant relationships among the subdimensions of authentic leadership, organisational citizenship behaviour, and job crafting within the nursing workforce of the Vhembe District, Limpopo Province, South Africa.

Notably, the Moral Perspective dimension of authentic leadership did not demonstrate significant associations with any subdimensions of organisational citizenship behaviour or job crafting, suggesting differential effects across authentic leadership components. The results substantiate the conceptual framework positioning authentic leadership as a predictor variable influencing both organisational citizenship behaviour and job crafting as outcome variables.

Consequently, the first research hypothesis (H1: "A statistically significant relationship exists between authentic leadership, organisational citizenship behaviour, and job crafting among nurses in the Vhembe District, Limpopo Province, South Africa") receives empirical support and is therefore accepted.

The second research hypothesis (H2: "Authentic leadership significantly influences organisational citizenship behaviour and job crafting behaviour among nurses in the Vhembe District, Limpopo Province, South Africa") is similarly supported by the correlation analysis findings.

Relationship between Authentic Leadership and Organisational Citizenship Behaviour

The correlation analysis revealed a substantial positive association ($r = 0.614, p < 0.001$) between authentic leadership and organisational citizenship behaviour, indicating that authentic leadership practices facilitate nurses' engagement in discretionary behaviours that extend beyond prescribed role requirements and contribute to enhanced organisational effectiveness.

Relationship between Authentic Leadership and Job Crafting

Similarly, a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.596, p < 0.001$) was established between authentic leadership and job crafting behaviours, demonstrating that authentic leadership practices create conducive conditions for nurses to proactively modify and redesign aspects of their work roles to align with their values, strengths, and motivations.

Based on these empirical findings, the second research hypothesis (H2: "Authentic leadership significantly influences organisational citizenship behaviour & job crafting behaviour among nurses in the Vhembe District, Limpopo Province, South Africa") received statistical support and was therefore accepted.

These results provide compelling evidence for the interconnected nature of these theoretical constructs while simultaneously identifying specific leadership dimensions that demonstrate greater efficacy in promoting beneficial workplace behaviours among nursing personnel. The robust and statistically significant correlations observed between Relational Transparency and various outcome measures, including Helping Colleagues, Engaging in Proactive Problem Solving, and Task Crafting, underscore the critical importance of transparent communication processes and evidence-based decision-making capabilities in cultivating collaborative and proactive organisational climates within healthcare settings.

Discussion and Findings of the Study

The empirical findings of this research demonstrate strong

convergence with contemporary theoretical frameworks and extant literature, substantiating the pivotal role of authentic leadership in cultivating positive organisational behaviours among healthcare personnel. The results corroborate the argument that nurses who perceive their supervisors as demonstrating ethical integrity, transparent communication, and supportive management practices exhibit enhanced propensity to engage in extra-role behaviours that transcend prescribed job requirements while simultaneously adapting their work roles to align with personal competencies and professional aspirations.

This study's findings align with recent research by Dirik (2024) who emphasised that authentic leadership and nurse empowerment are essential in creating healthy work environments and delivering safe, high-quality care. The empirical evidence supports the theoretical propositions advanced by Avolio et al. (2004) and Walumbwa et al. (2008) who posited that authentic leaders' ethical conduct serves as a catalyst for subordinates' voluntary engagement in organisationally beneficial behaviours beyond formal role expectations. However, this study's findings present a notable departure from established literature regarding the influence of moral leadership dimensions, as the Strong Moral Code component demonstrated no significant associations with either organisational citizenship behaviours or job crafting behaviours among the study participants.

This divergence may reflect the unique sociocultural and organisational contexts characterising South African healthcare institutions, thereby presenting compelling avenues for future research. The contextual specificity of leadership effectiveness has been increasingly recognised in contemporary organisational behaviour literature, particularly within developing healthcare systems where resource constraints and systemic challenges may moderate traditional leadership-outcome relationships.

Recent literature has emphasised the critical importance of nursing leadership in healthcare outcomes. Contemporary research demonstrates that nursing leadership styles are significantly associated with organisational, employee, and patient outcomes, with evidence-based leadership approaches showing measurable positive effects on nurse leaders' performance and clinical outcomes (Cummings et al., 2021). Furthermore, recent studies have specifically examined how authentic leadership influences nurses' psychological well-being, demonstrating its capacity to reduce workplace stressors and enhance professional satisfaction (Ribeiro et al., 2022).

The study revealed that job crafting facilitates efficient resource management and subsequently influences prosocial behaviours, aligning with Demerouti's (2015) theoretical framework, which conceptualises job crafting as a proactive behaviour that enables employees to optimise their work-related resources and challenges, ultimately enhancing organisational citizenship behaviours. This finding is further corroborated by recent research indicating that creative nurses tend to engage in job crafting more frequently, which is positively associated with their subjective well-being.

The empirical evidence demonstrates that leadership characterised by relational transparency, balanced cognitive processing, and authentic self-expression creates organisational climates that empower employees to engage in proactive work redesign, implement innovative problem-solving approaches, and demonstrate collegial support behaviours. This phenomenon

assumes particular significance within healthcare contexts, where collaborative relationships, creative problem-solving capabilities, and evidence-based decision-making processes directly influence patient care quality and service delivery effectiveness.

The absence of significant correlations between Strong Moral Code and the examined outcome variables warrants careful consideration. While moral leadership remains theoretically and ethically important, this finding suggests that its direct influence on specific dimensions of organisational citizenship behaviour and job crafting may be mediated by other contextual or individual factors within the South African healthcare environment.

Strategic Implications for South African Healthcare Management

These findings carry substantial implications for healthcare administration and organisational development within South African public health institutions. The cultivation of authentic leadership practices represents a strategic imperative for healthcare organisations seeking to enhance nursing staff engagement, improve patient care outcomes, and strengthen organisational effectiveness. Healthcare administrators should prioritise the implementation of comprehensive leadership development initiatives that emphasise authenticity, transparency, and ethical conduct to foster positive work environments and optimise organisational performance.

The empirical validation of relationships between authentic leadership, organisational citizenship behaviour, and job crafting provides evidence-based support for targeted interventions aimed at developing nursing leadership capabilities. This is particularly relevant given the numerous multifaceted issues that continue to pose serious challenges to nursing education and training in South Africa.

Recommendations for South African Public Healthcare Sector

Leadership Development Framework

Healthcare institutions should establish structured mentorship programmes that pair experienced nurse leaders with emerging professionals, focusing on developing authentic leadership competencies through experiential learning and reflective practice. These programmes should incorporate cultural contexts and address the unique challenges facing the national healthcare system.

Organisational Culture Transformation

The transition from traditional hierarchical leadership models to authentic, participative leadership approaches requires systematic cultural change management. Healthcare organisations should implement change management strategies that emphasise transparent communication, shared decision-making, and ethical leadership practices as foundational elements of organisational culture.

Policy Integration

The South African National Department of Health should consider integrating authentic leadership principles into nursing competency frameworks and professional development standards. This integration would ensure consistent application of evidence-based leadership practices across public healthcare institutions nationwide.

Resource Allocation and Support Systems

Healthcare administrators should allocate resources for leadership training programmes while establishing support systems that enable nurses to engage in job crafting activities. This includes providing protected time for professional development, creating mentorship opportunities, and establishing recognition systems for organisational citizenship behaviours.

Measurement and Evaluation Systems

Healthcare institutions should implement systematic evaluation mechanisms to assess leadership effectiveness and its impact on patient outcomes, staff satisfaction, and organisational performance. Regular assessment of authentic leadership practices will enable continuous improvement and evidence-based refinement of leadership development strategies.

Future Research Directions

The unexpected finding regarding Strong Moral Code's lack of association with outcome variables presents opportunities for future investigation within South African healthcare contexts. Researchers should explore potential mediating factors, cultural influences, and contextual variables that may moderate these relationships. Additionally, longitudinal studies examining the sustainability and long-term effects of authentic leadership interventions would contribute valuable insights to the field.

Conclusion

This study contributes significantly to the expanding knowledge base regarding leadership effects on employee behaviour within healthcare environments. The results underscore the fundamental importance of authentic leadership in promoting organisational citizenship behaviour and job crafting among nursing professionals. The empirical evidence supports strategic investments in leadership development programmes that prioritise authenticity, transparency, and ethical behaviour as mechanisms for creating positive work environments and enhancing overall organisational effectiveness within the South African healthcare sector.

The paradigmatic shift from conventional leadership approaches toward transparent communication and rational decision-making processes represents a critical pathway for encouraging nurses to engage in behaviours that simultaneously promote individual professional growth and organisational success, ultimately contributing to improved healthcare service delivery across South African public health institutions.

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Data Availability

The data cannot be made available because the researcher declared to adhere to the ethical principles of protection of the participants' information, protect their anonymity and would rather reapply for a new ethical procedure to acquire their consent.

Authors Contribution

Mphephu Phumudzo: Conceptualisation of the proposal, literature review, Methodology, data collection, and data presentation.

Leboho Tlabo: Literature review, methodology, data interpretation, data analysis, final write-up and editing.

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